

The Mapping and Planetary Spatial Infrastructure Team (MAPSIT) is a community-based, interdisciplinary forum for the discussion, analysis, and representation of matters concerning the creation and development of planetary geographic information and cartographic products, a program of sustained planetary geologic mapping, and the tools necessary for these capabilities. This is a report of MAPSIT’s findings, produced by the Steering Committee with inputs solicited from the broader community.

Findings from 2025 Calendar Year

- **MAPSIT appreciates the ongoing Planetary Data Ecosystem (PDE) Responses (e.g., [Ferguson et al., 2024](#)) and encourages continued responses.** The PDE is a framework designed to support NASA science by making data more accessible, discoverable, and usable for researchers, educators, and the broader community. It connects NASA’s planetary missions with data analysis, data validation, data standards, software development, training opportunities, and research initiatives. Currently, the PDE website (<https://planetary.data.nasa.gov/>) serves as a central hub for planetary science resources, expanding the reach of planetary data and tools. It is an important component of open data and science. MAPSIT encourages continued NASA support and investment in the PDE. The PDE is more than data and data-preservation, it also contains the people, resources, and tools needed to maximize the use of planetary data (e.g., in the PDS). MAPSIT applauds the long-term goals of the PDE that ensure data are usable by the widest possible audience now and over the long term.
- **MAPSIT encourages continued investments in coordinated mapping programs for high-priority exploration sites.** The Lunar Mapping Program (LMaP) was set up

by NASA Planetary Science Division (PSD) to support upcoming missions, such as Artemis. A continuation of this program was included in the ROSES-2025 announcement of opportunity. MAPSIT applauds and encourages continued NASA support of coordinated and responsive mapping efforts at multiple scales as needed for upcoming destinations such as the Moon and other bodies.

MAPSIT is pleased with the progress of the Lunar Mapping Program Year 1 cohort as reported at the October 2025 GSA annual meeting, and that NASA is continuing the program for a second year. MAPSIT encourages NASA to continue to support geologic mapping via LMaP as part of Artemis mission planning activities.

MAPSIT encourages NASA to support completion of Venus quadrangle geologic maps in future proposal calls. Many Venus quadrangle maps were started in the 1990s using Magellan data, but the Venus Mapping Program had its funding cut prematurely. Ideally, these maps would be completed before the VERITAS, DAVINCI, and/or EnVISION missions begin operations at Venus.

MAPSIT endorses the establishment of a NASA-supported Europa quadrangle geologic mapping program in 2031 after the Europa Clipper primary mission begins. This will require geologic mapping training activities for the community in at least the prior year.

- **MAPSIT reiterates the importance of Planetary Spatial Data Infrastructures (PSDIs) in order to increase spatial data interoperability and usability.** A three-year effort, which was USGS-led and NASA-supported, to establish and mature spatial data infrastructures for Europa and the Moon, both high-priority exploration targets, will not be continued by these organizations into FY2026. Although the activity timeframe was brief, MAPSIT recognizes that the efforts and contributions from these planetary spatial data infrastructures (PSDIs) had significant impact. Further conversations within the broader community, including PSD, should seek longer-term, sustainable solutions to PSDIs and evaluate the lessons learned from this experience.

- **MAPSIT sees a need for continued coordinated international mapping and data standards communications and encourages continued NASA PSD engagement in and support of such activities.** With broad funding and travel limitations within NASA and affecting many contractors, MAPSIT is concerned that PSD engagement in international coordination activities, either directly or through proxies, is at risk. Furthermore, activities related to international mapping, standards, and mission coordination should be sustainable and efficient. MAPSIT encourages additional conversations with stakeholders to find solutions to sustain these coordinated activities.

One way to sustain these efforts is through national and international workshops that focus on planetary data and focused working groups like the Planetary Geologic Mappers (PGM). PGM activities were historically supported through interagency cooperation with the USGS and, most recently, the MAPSIT AG. However, due to increasing limitations on travel, meetings, and travel support, the Planetary Geologic Mappers meetings have been a challenge to sustain without additional programmatic support. MAPSIT encourages enhancing the NASA support of the Planetary Geologic Mappers working group, which serves to generate and review community best-practices for planetary geologic mapping.

- **MAPSIT reiterates the value and importance of planetary data and tools training and workshops.** NASA has supported workshops, both in-person and virtual, that provide essential training in highly specialized planetary data and analysis methods. These events have been very successful and are well attended. A recent report from the Office of the Chief Science Data Officer about tracking metrics for publications, data, and software linked to NASA-funded Earth and space science research under the SPD-41a guidelines ([https://assets.science.nasa.gov/content/dam/science/cds/about-us/ocsdo/reports/SPD-41a Metrics Report v2.pdf](https://assets.science.nasa.gov/content/dam/science/cds/about-us/ocsdo/reports/SPD-41a%20Metrics%20Report%20v2.pdf)) underscores how investments made in conveying NASA data guidelines and encouraging the adoption of desired practices amongst researchers and data providers could improve the outcomes. Within the PSD community, planetary data and tools training sessions and workshops have become a vital resource for both data and data providers, and MAPSIT encourages continued support of these activities. The Topical Workshops Symposiums and Conferences (TWSC) funding line has supported many of these efforts in recent years with great success; however, MAPSIT is very concerned about the discontinuation of TWSC, and the lack of clarity on a viable replacement avenue to support necessary training and workshops. This concern is further amplified by the increasing restrictions on travel and meeting attendance for many in the community. Although virtual workshops and training events are frequently highly effective, a lack of options for in-person training will significantly impact the benefits of such efforts in many cases as well as hamper opportunities for networking and community building.

- **MAPSIT is extremely concerned about the lack of Interagency Funding in ROSES-2025 as mapping, data standards, data production, research, and other programs are often built on interagency communication and cooperation.** Limiting funding to only one agency (i.e., NASA) severely reduces participation and the creativity of research. This can lead to stove-piping of tools and data standards, critical gaps, duplicated efforts, and inefficiency. MAPSIT encourages finding long-term solutions that can be quickly implemented (in contrast to the, often, long setup time needed to establish Interagency Agreements) to enable collaboration and broader

cooperation. This can help ensure that planetary data continues to enable the widest possible range of use-cases and applications without long delays.

MAPSIT encourages PSD research and analysis (R&A) funding structures that fully accommodate geologic mapping, including USGS-grade products. In prior years, peer-reviewed geologic mapping for the pursuit of one or more lines of research would not always fit well into the available R&A programs (such as PDART or body-specific Data Analysis Programs), frustrating efforts. Current and future R&A programs should be fully inclusive of geologic mapping as part of scientific research and should consider geologic mapping approaches to perform investigations as fully relevant. Furthermore, peer-review of maps by the USGS requires interagency participation, and MAPSIT is concerned that the ongoing funding limitations (e.g., few options for Interagency Agreements, and very long setup times) are further inhibiting the timely production of mission critical products, creating uncertainties and delays for upcoming exploration objectives.